

1 **The androgen and estrogen receptor are silenced in the cervix during progression from CIN2/3 to**
2 **cervical carcinoma.**

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7 We studied total transcription in the cervix during transformation in vivo in humans. The role of estrogen
8 and androgens in breast and prostate cancer is more widely understood than in the cervix. We discovered
9 that silencing of androgen and estrogen receptors was likely a requisite transcriptional event during
10 progression from CIN2/3 to carcinoma. The data allude to a cervix-specific hormone receptor event during
11 progression to transformation but do not disclose the existence of a transcriptional event involving the
12 estrogen receptor that occurs during transformation in all cells.

- 13 1. Supporting data: The progesterone receptor PGR and a molecule that likely functions as a
14 co-receptor for the estrogen receptor, GREB1, are regulated with or directly controlled by AR and ESR1.
 - 15 2. Oncogenic homeobox *PBX1* is an AR and ESR1 co-regulated target.
 - 16 3. AR and ESR1 co-regulated targets include genes important for development and regeneration
17 including RAI2, BMPR1B and IGF1.
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